

Yield performance and agronomic characteristics of deep water rices, 1984 monsoon season, 0 Mon, Vietnam.

Designation	Plant ht (cm)	Flowering date	Panicles/m ²	Filled grains/panicle	Sterility (%)	1000-grain wt (g)	Yield ^a (t/ha)
Trang Chum	208	26 Dec	63	147	10	26.7	4.0 a
Radine China 4	168	15 Dec	48	235	10	22.3	4.0 a
Chum Ruot Mua	149	20 Nov	54	173	8	23.2	3.6 a
Mot Bui Sel. 28	132	1 Dec	39	145	12	25.0	3.0 b
Ba Thiet	146	11 Nov	45	135	17	26.0	3.0 b
Lua Phi	138	29 Nov	40	180	13	23.6	2.8 b
Trang Lun	137	16 Dec	40	149	5	23.2	2.7 b
Lem Lun	149	18 Dec	49	130	17	30.0	2.7 b
Mot Bui Sel. 139	141	1 Dec	51	143	17	23.5	2.5 b
523 (IR8608/Truong Hung)	145	10 Oct	45	90	20	30.0	2.5 b
Trai May	166	20 Nov	54	129	15	26.8	1.8 c
Tat No	148	10 Dec	40	130	27	23.5	1.6 c
522 (Trai May Cut/424)	140	10 Oct	45	139	18	25.3	1.4 c

F= 19.679**
CV = 11.67%

^a Values followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Ruot Mua yielded best. They flowered after the peak water level and had low sterility. Radine China 4, which has tolerance for acid sulfate soil, had the most filled grains per panicle. *ℒ*

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Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

ADVERSE SOILS TOLERANCE

Effect of Zn on electrical conductivity (EC), endosperm weight, germination, and vigor of three rices

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We studied the effect of Zn on physiological parameters related to seed and seedling growth of Jaya, IR20, and Kanchi in 1980-81. Rice seeds were soaked in water in a 2.5, 5, 10, 15, and 20 ppm Zn solution for 16 h. EC of the leachates and endosperm weight after seed soaking, percent germination, and seedling vigor were recorded. Seedling vigor was computed as germination percentage × mean dry weight of a normal seedling.

EC of the leachates increased with increasing Zn concentration, and appeared to affect germination. An increase in leachates lowered percent germination. Jaya had highest EC. Maximum endosperm weight for all varieties was with 5 ppm Zn. IR20 had significantly higher endosperm weight at 5 to 10 ppm Zn than the other varieties. Increased endosperm weight may

Effect of Zn on EC, endosperm weight, germination, and vigor of Jaya, IR20, and Kanchi, Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment	EC (mmho/cm)	Endosperm weight (mg)	Germination (%)	Vigor ^a
<i>Jaya</i>				
Water	0.370	23.5	92	152
Zn (ppm)				
2.5	0.325	22.5	96	162
5.0	0.430	29.3	99	173
10.0	0.485	23.3	92	170
15.0	0.495	19.5	91	132
20.0	0.490	20.7	90	123
<i>IR20</i>				
Water	0.125	29.7	100	150
Zn (ppm)				
2.5	0.100	31.3	100	158
5.0	0.110	37.0	100	184
10.0	0.130	36.0	100	172
15.0	0.170	30.6	96	143
20.0	0.220	34.0	92	139
<i>Kanchi</i>				
Water	0.110	28.1	100	172
Zn (ppm)				
2.5	0.110	27.6	100	182
5.0	0.090	28.8	100	189
10.0	0.120	27.8	98	188
15.0	0.150	28.4	97	189
20.0	0.140	28.2	97	162
Variety CD (P = 0.05)	0.021	0.00027	3	—
Treatments CD (P = 0.05)	0.030	0.00038	4	—

^a Vigor index = Germination percentage × mean dry weight (mg) of a seedling from a standard germination test.

influence seedling vigor, presumably through auxin-mediated metabolism.

Jaya and IR20 germination declined as Zn increased. Kanchi had 97%

germination even at 20 ppm Zn. Values for vigor, which is considered a reliable index of seed potency, indicated that all the varieties performed best at 5 ppm Zn. Higher concentrations (15 and 20

ppm) reduced Jaya and IR20 vigor, but not that of Kanchi (see table). EC of the seed leachates after soaking in Zn was negatively correlated with

germination and seedling vigor. Zn had little effect on endosperm weight, but germination percentage was closely related to seed treatment. *S*

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization HYBRID RICE

Ratoon regeneration in rices and their single-cross hybrids after three cuttings

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Sixteen single-cross hybrids of 15 rice varieties were planted in Aug 1982 at Main Research Station, Bangalore. F2 seeds were harvested on 24 Jan, 20 Aug, and 10 Dec 1983. After the third ratooning, stubble was left in situ or transplanted in single rows containing 30 slips. Thirty-five days after cutting and transplanting, plant height and number of tillers per plant were recorded (see table). Plant height was measured from the ground to the tip of the topmost leaf.

Hybrids had greater regeneration capacity than varieties. Hybrid TN1/Type 3 had the best regeneration ability. Among varieties, Type 3 had good regeneration. Many varieties could not be propagated in situ after the third cutting. Vegetative propagation of

Plant height and tillers per plant on 20 plants 35 d after thud cutting.

	Plant height (cm)		Tillers (no.)	
	In situ	Transplanted	In situ	Transplanted
<i>Cross</i>				
TNI/Type 3	56.2±3.6	67.4±1.7	24.7±4.0	14.8±4.7
Jaya/Type 3	54.9±1.9	53.0±1.4	31.9±5.5	7.2±0.4
PK150/Basumathi	54.5±3.6	21.0±3.5	31.1±4.1	2.0±0.4
Mashuri/Doddi	51.1±1.4	45.9±2.5	19.1±3.1	3.6±0.4
Mashuri/Prakash	46.9±1.9	39.8±2.3	22.2±3.7	5.4±0.5
IET7031/Telahamsa	44.1±1.8	35.1±2.6	20.4±2.9	1.9±0.5
SHM 1/Intan Mutant 1	44.2±1.7	32.8±8.6	7.1±1.4	3.3±0.5
Type 3/Telahamsa	44.3±1.8	47.0±1.5	22.8±1.6	10.5±0.7
TNI/Telahamsa	39.4±1.4	30.1±1.5	18.3±2.2	3.8±0.7
Jaya/Telahamsa	35.6±2.1	30.5±4.2	12.3±1.5	2.6±0.5
Jaya/Mashuri	38.5±1.3	34.3±1.7	20.3±2.7	4.8±0.5
Jaya/IET7031	38.4±2.3	32.3±2.4	16.0±1.1	2.5±0.5
PK150/IR36	37.9±2.6	28.2±1.9	18.2±1.9	4.4±0.6
Mangla/Telahamsa	37.1±0.9	33.4±1.6	19.0±3.2	3.0±0.4
PK177/Intan Mutant 1	36.8±1.5	34.6±1.3	14.2±1.5	5.1±0.6
IET7031/Mangla	36.4±4.3	30.6±2.9	6.6±3.9	3.1±0.6
<i>Variety</i>				
Type 3	52.3±3.9	53.9±2.1	14.8±2.6	3.8±0.4
Jaya	29.8±3.5	31.7±2.1	7.7±0.9	3.2±0.4
Mangla	36.7±2.9	34.3±1.9	3.7±2.2	4.2±0.3
Telahamsa	37.4±0.9	27.2±1.6	15.3±3.1	2.5±0.3
Mashuri	42.4±2.2	36.4±1.6	—	4.3±0.4
TN1	—	29.1±1.9	—	4.1±0.5
Prakash	—	34.3±2.1	—	4.7±0.4
Intan Mutant 1	—	45.3±2.6	—	4.7±0.7
Doddi	—	50.6±1.5	—	3.9±0.7

single-cross hybrids allows continuous production of F2 seeds and maximizes

the population size of the second segregating generation of any cross. *S*

Performance of male-sterile and maintainer lines and crosses

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We evaluated Chinese cytoplasmic male-sterile (cms) lines V20A and Zhen Shan 97A and corresponding maintainers V20B and Zhen Shan 97B in 1983 wet and 1984 dry season at CLDRRI. In wet season, they matured early and had low phenotypic acceptability (scale 5),

Table 1. Agronomic traits of cms lines and maintainers at O Mon, Hau Giang, Vietnam.

Line	Duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Panicles/m ²	Grains/panicle	Sterility (%)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Yield (t/ha)
<i>1983 wet season</i>							
V20A	89	75	304				
V20B	91	67	274	74	38	29	2.9
Zhen Shan 97A	93	73	218				
Zhen Shan 97B	97	69	212	137	27	27	2.2
<i>1984 dry season</i>							
V20A	90	71	363				
V20B	97	71	284	74	16	30	2.3
Zhen Shan 97A	93	68	297				
Zhen Shan 97B	103	74	269	97	26	28	2.8